

Spectrophotometric Study on the Complexation Reaction of Platinum(IV) with Perphenazine

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Perphenazine forms a purple coloured complex with platinum(IV) in hydrochloric acid-sodium acetate buffer containing copper catalyst. The complex has an absorption maximum at 528 nm with molar absorptivity 1.289×10^4 l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The sensitivity of the reaction is 15.15 ng/cm². Beer's law is valid over the concentration range 0.5-8.5 ppm of platinum(IV) with optimum concentration range 0.9-8.4 ppm. Continuous variations, mole ratio and slope ratio methods indicate 1 : 1 composition for the complex. The effects of pH, time, temperature, order of addition of reagents, reagent concentration and interferences from various ions are reported. The reagent is successfully used for the determination of platinum in minerals and alloys.

BEAMISH¹ reported the deficiencies of many of the spectrophotometric methods for the determination of platinum. Many methods involved either heating for a long time for maximum colour development. For example acetyl acetone², acenaphthenequinone monoxime³, sodium 4-(mercapto acetamido) benzene sulphate⁴ and *o*-hydroxy thiobenzhydrazide⁵ required heating for a period varying from 15 min to 5 hours. Reagents like potassium iodide⁶, dibenzylthioxamide⁷, 2,3-quinoxaline dithiol⁸, and benzoin- α -oxime⁹ required 30 min to 18 hours to give maximum colour development. Other reagents like tin(II) chloride¹⁰, *p*-nitrosodimethyl aniline¹¹, 5-(*p*-dimethylaminobenzylidene) rhodanine¹² and *o*-phenylenediamine¹³ could not tolerate the interferences from base and platinum metals. In the present paper the authors have investigated the complexation reaction between platinum(IV) and perphenazine (PP), 4-[3-(2-chlorophenothiazine-10-yl) propyl]-1-piperazine ethanol dihydrochloride and developed PP as a sensitive reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of platinum(IV).

Experimental

Apparatus: A Beckman Model DB spectrophotometer with stoppered silica cells of 1-cm optical path was used for absorbance measurements.

Reagents:

Standard platinum (IV) solution:

A known weight of platinum wire (99.99% pure) was dissolved in hot aqua regia and the solution was evaporated almost to dryness. The residue was treated with 5 ml of conc. hydrochloric acid and evaporated to a small volume. This treatment was repeated for five times in order to destroy any nitroso complexes formed. The resulting residue after final evaporation was then

dissolved and diluted to 1 litre with 1 *M* hydrochloric acid. The stock solution was further diluted as needed.

PP solution:

0.5% w/v aqueous solution of the reagent containing one drop of 1 *M* hydrochloric acid was prepared and stored in an amber coloured bottle in a refrigerator.

Copper(II) solution:

0.1 *M* copper(II) solution was prepared from BDH AnalaR copper(II) sulphate.

Buffer solutions:

Buffer solutions in the pH range 0.65-5.2 were prepared from 1 *M* hydrochloric acid and 1 *M* sodium acetate.

All other reagents were of analytical grade and were used without further purification.

Recommended procedure for spectrophotometric determinations:

An aliquot of the sample solution containing 12-213 μ g of platinum(IV), 5 ml of hydrochloric acid-sodium acetate buffer, 1 ml of 0.1 *M* copper(II) sulphate solution and 6 ml of 0.5% PP solution were taken in a 25 ml volumetric flask and the solution was diluted to the mark with doubly distilled water. The solution was mixed well and the absorbance was measured at 528 nm after 25 min against a corresponding reagent blank prepared in the same manner. The amount of platinum in the sample solution was then deduced from the previously prepared standard calibration curve.

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Results and Discussion

PP is soluble in water containing 1-2 drops of 1 *M* hydrochloric acid giving a colourless solution. Initial experiments showed that PP reacts with platinum(IV) very slowly at room temperature ($27^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$) in hydrochloric, sulphuric, phosphoric or acetic acid or hydrochloric acid-sodium acetate buffer. The reagent complexes with platinum(IV) rapidly in the presence of copper(II) which appears to act as a catalyst. The study of platinum(IV)-PP complex in hydrochloric, sulphuric, phosphoric or acetic acid media is not recommended because the sensitivity and the stability of the complex are very much less. The buffer medium was therefore selected.

Effect of pH

The optimum pH range for the formation of purple complex was found to be 1.4–3.0. The absorbance of the complex decreased above pH 3.0. A buffer medium of pH 2.1 was conveniently chosen for all further work.

Spectral Characteristics

The absorption spectra of the platinum(IV)-PP complex, reagent blank and platinum(IV) are shown in Fig. 1. The maximum absorbance of the complex is found at 526-530 nm. The absorption spectra of the reagent blank and platinum(IV) under similar conditions show that they do not absorb appreciably around this wavelength. All subsequent studies were carried out at 528 nm.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of platinum-PP complex, Reagent blank and Platinum(IV).

- (A) Platinum (IV)-PP complex in hydrochloric acid-sodium acetate buffer, pH 2.1 containing 1000 ppm of Cu(II). (Concentration of platinum(IV)=4ppm).
- (B) Reagent blank in hydrochloric acid-sodium acetate buffer, pH 2.1 containing 1000 ppm of Cu(II). (Concentration of PP= $2.52 \times 10^{-3} M$).
- (C) Platinum(IV) in hydrochloric acid-sodium acetate buffer, pH 2.1.

Rate of reaction and stability of colour

The colour of the complex is fully developed in 25 min after mixing the reagents and an essentially constant absorbance is obtained over at least 60 min.

Effect of varying reagent concentration

The effect of reagent concentration has been investigated by measuring the absorbance at 528 nm of solutions containing 4 ppm of platinum(IV) and varying the amount of reagent. It is found that the maximum colour formation is attained with fifty-fold molar excess of the reagent over platinum. 6 ml of 0.5% reagent solution in a final volume of 25 ml is necessary for less than 8.5 ppm of platinum.

Effect of copper(II) concentration

The maximum complexation is attained only in the presence of copper(II) which does not react with PP but catalyses the reaction between platinum(IV) and PP. The effective copper concentration has been found to be 1000-3000 ppm of copper(II). Below 1000 ppm the time required for complete complexation increases with decreasing concentration of copper(II). Above 3000 ppm, the absorbance value slightly decreases with an increase in the concentration of copper. Hence a concentration of 1000 ppm of copper(II) was chosen for all further work.

Sequence of addition of reagents

There is no appreciable change in the absorbance of colour of the complex if the order of addition of the reagents is varied.

Effect of varying temperature

The complex has been investigated at temperatures ranging from 5-70°. The absorbance values are insensitive to temperature in the range 5-52°.

Calibration, range and sensitivity

The platinum(IV)-PP complex obeys Beer's law over the concentration range 0.5-8.5 ppm. The optimum working range as evaluated by Ringbom's method^{14,15} is 0.9-8.5 ppm. The molar absorptivity is $1.289 \times 10^4 l \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. According to Sandell's expression¹⁶, the sensitivity of the reaction is 15.15 ng/cm^2 .

Precision and Accuracy

The precision and accuracy of the method have been evaluated by analysing solutions containing known amounts of platinum(IV). The results are presented in Table 1.

Effect of diverse ions

In order to assess the possible analytical applications of platinum(IV)-PP complex, the effects of some ions which often accompany platinum were studied by adding different amounts of ionic species to 100 μg of platinum in solution in 25 ml volumetric flasks and the

TABLE 1—PRECISION AND ACCURACY

Experiment	Platinum(IV), ppm		Relative error %	Standard deviation, ppm
	Taken	Found		
1	1.00	1.00	—	—
2	2.00	1.99	-0.5	0.0294
3	3.00	2.97	-1.0	0.0439
4	4.00	4.00	—	—
5	5.00	4.97	-0.6	0.0518
6	6.00	6.08	+1.33	0.0110

TABLE 2—TOLERANCE LIMIT OF DIVERSE IONS IN THE DETERMINATION OF 4 PPM OF PLATINUM(IV).

Ion added	Tolerance limit ppm	Ion added	Tolerance limit ppm
F ⁻	2,800	Ir(III)	74.0
Cl ⁻	10,000	Ru(III)	0.6
Br ⁻	4,000	Ru(III)	3.0**
I ₂	2.0	Fe(III)	1.0
NO ₂	10,000	Fe(III)	4.0***
SO ₄ ²⁻	10,000	Os(VIII)	10.0
PO ₄ ³⁻	1,500	Pb(II)	160.0
S ₂ O ₈ ²⁻	0.25	Co(II)	280.0
Oxalate	250	Ni(II)	400.0
Citrate	1,000	Ag(I)	12.0
Tartrate	3,000	Zn(II)	2,000
DMG	175	Cd(II)	1,600
EDTA	800	Al(III)	900
Au(III)	0.4	Cr(III)	60
Pd(II)	0.5	Se(IV)	2,800
Pd(II)	2.5*	Te(IV)	100
Rh(III)	72.0	Ti(IV)	400
		W(VI)	40

* in the presence of 160 ppm of DMG.

** in the presence of 750 ppm of EDTA.

*** in the presence of 1000 ppm of citrate.

colour was developed as described in the procedure. The tolerance limits are shown in Table 2. An error of 2% in the absorbance was considered tolerable.

Composition of the complex

The composition of platinum-PP complex was studied by continuous variations^{17,18}, mole ratio¹⁹ and slope ratio²⁰ methods. Job's method showed the stoichiometric ratio of platinum-PP to be 1:1 and this was confirmed by the mole ratio and slope ratio methods. The apparent stability constant of the complex as evaluated by mole ratio method has a log K value of 5.6363 ± 0.1 at 27°.

Nature of the complex

The nature of the complex was studied by passing an aliquot of the solution of the complex through the cation exchange resins, Dowex 50W-X8 and Amberlite IR-120(H). The complete absorbance of the coloured complex by the ionic exchangers has indicated that the complex is cationic.

Applications

Determination of platinum in alloys, thermocouples and minerals

Analysed samples of platinum-iridium (10-40% Ir), platinum-tungsten(4%W) and platinum-nickel(40-55%Ni)

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF PLATINUM IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURES CORRESPONDING TO ALLOYS, THERMOCOUPLES AND NEVJANSKITE.

	Pt taken (ppm)	Metal ion added (ppm)					Pt found ^a (ppm)
		Rh	Ir	Os	Ru	W	
Pt-Rh thermocouple	1.00	0.13	—	—	—	—	1.00
	2.00	0.26	—	—	—	—	2.01
	3.00	0.39	—	—	—	—	3.025
	4.00	0.52	—	—	—	—	4.05
Pt-Ir alloy	2.70	—	0.30	—	—	—	2.73
	3.80	—	0.20	—	—	—	3.85
	4.60	—	0.40	—	—	—	4.63
Pt-Ni alloy	2.3	—	—	—	—	2.7	2.30
	4.5	—	—	—	—	5.5	4.45
	6.0	—	—	—	—	4.0	5.96
Pt-W alloy	2.0	—	—	—	—	0.09	2.02
	3.0	—	—	—	—	0.14	3.00
	5.0	—	—	—	—	0.23	5.05
Nevjanskite	3.0	0.8	16.0	3.5	0.3	—	3.02
	4.0	1.0	31.0	6.5	0.5	—	3.98
	6.0	1.5	32.5	7.0	0.5	—	6.10

^a Average of five determinations.

alloys, platinum-rhodium (10-20% Rd) thermocouple and nevjanskite mineral (8-12% Pt, 62-65% Ir, 13-14% Rh and 1% Ru) were not available. Therefore, synthetic mixtures containing platinum and other metals corresponding to alloys, thermocouple and nevjanskite were prepared and the platinum content was determined following the standard procedure. The results are presented in Table 3.

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